

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE 2014 PRESIDENTIAL ELECTIONS: EXPLAINING ABSENTEEISM THROUGH THE PRISM OF POLITICAL FACTORS

Mushchenko Ya.

*a Third-year Graduate Student,
at the Department of Political Science and International Relations
of Lviv Polytechnic National University
Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-7207-4533*

Abstract

Voter turnout is considered to be one of the most important indicators of political engagement, but national electoral activity in Ukraine is characterized by a systematic decline, which may indicate various political trends, such as disinterest, frustration, lack of understanding of processes, apathy, etc. In this context, it is relevant to study the political mentality and reasons for the electoral non-participation of Ukrainian voters. Certainly, some motives will be common to citizens of different countries, but national specifics and the context make their own adjustments and influence the electorate's decision in different ways.

The 2014 elections were uniquely held in one round but were marked by the lowest turnout (60% of citizens) in the presidential election in the entire electoral history of Ukraine. In our opinion, political factors may explain the decision of citizens to abstain from voting.

Analyzing the dynamics of turnout in Ukraine's presidential elections since 1991, researchers emphasize the obvious drop in participation since the 1990s. If we started with 85% electoral participation (1991), the elections of recent years show a figure of 60% in 2014, 63% and 61% in 2019 (1st and 2nd rounds, respectively). It is worth adding a note that the level of turnout is directly affected by the relevance of the population census data (which has not been conducted in Ukraine since 2001), and therefore it can be assumed that the decline in turnout is also due to an overestimation of the population and, accordingly, the electorate [1].

The question we seek to address is why Ukrainians do not vote. The author's own classification of political factors of absenteeism, understanding of the context and course of the 2014 presidential election, as well as the use of a number of methods (in particular, historical, comparative, systemic, structural and functional, analysis of documents and statistics, analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, etc.) are essential for answering this question.

Keywords: absenteeism, electoral participation, political factors, presidential campaign, national specificity, war.

According to the author's classification of political factors of absenteeism, we will focus on the following variables to analyze the portrait of the Ukrainian voter:

A) a group of institutional and normative factors (type of political system; party system; type of electoral system; voter registration system; turnout threshold; mandatory vote; alternative voting methods);

B) a group of situational or conjunctural factors (level of competition in elections; list and characteristics of electoral subjects; simultaneity of elections; nature of the election campaign and level of corruption and fraud);

C) a group of value-motivational or value-oriented factors (level of political culture and consciousness; type of political ideology; political regime; media and social media coverage of elections; trust in public authorities).

The context of the 2014 elections was the unprecedented early election of the fifth president of Ukraine, which took place in the face of the annexation of Crimea, the occupation of parts of Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts, the self-removal of Viktor Yanukovich, the Revolution of Dignity, the outbreak of war in the east of Ukraine, the established intention to integrate into Europe and reject Russia, etc. The 2014 elections were also seen as a turning point for Ukraine's new future.

Twenty-one candidates took part in the early elections, with three candidates acting as real antagonists.

The political system – the Constitutional Court of Ukraine's decision of 2010 canceled the 2004 reform, and therefore in 2010 Ukraine actually returned to a presidential-parliamentary republic with a significant expansion of presidential powers, including through control over the executive branch. As we can see, such a decision and its practical consequences were not successful, and therefore in 2014 there was a return to a parliamentary-presidential republic (the decision of the Constitutional Court of 2010 was recognized as illegal by the majority of the Verkhovna Rada).

The party system of 2013-2014 – the party system after the revolutionary events of 2014 underwent radical changes. The crisis of the party system is quite evident, as the decades-long accumulated problems of the national party system (lack of institutionalization, inability to represent the real needs of even the target electorate; lack of ideology development and consistency in activities; excessive personalization of political parties; large number of parties; irregularity of party activities; instability of the party system in general; gaps in legislation; fragmentation and polarization, etc). A clear indicator of changes in the party system is the emergence of new players in the political arena. In particular, the only party whose activities can be traced

back years is the Yulia Tymoshenko Bloc. All the other parties were either newcomers or were disbanded and then reorganized into new political forces (the so-called rebranding). Interestingly, such changes were accompanied by support and changes in the electoral behavior of Ukrainian citizens, as for the first time since the 1990s, the electorate actively expressed trust in new political forces (including, for example, the People's Front, Petro Poroshenko Bloc, UDAR, Samopomich, etc.). At the same time, the once-powerful Communist Party has disappeared from the political arena. The revolution helped to renew the party system and marked a new stage of political struggle for supporters. However, it should be emphasized that the problems of oligarchic financing, fragmentation and personalization of parties have not disappeared. The party system of 2014 contributed to the emergence of prerequisites for the consolidation of society. In particular, for the first time since 2002, parties (including the Opposition Bloc and others) did not emphasize linguistic and regional differences; extremist parties were marginalized; the regional split softened; and a definite course was formed. The 2014 shock therapy was a hope for a more functional, stable, and better institutionalized party system.

The type of electoral system is a majority system of absolute majority (50%+1, second round).

Voter registration system – passive (automatic) voter registration.

Turnout threshold – the minimum turnout threshold in Ukraine has been abolished since 1998 (in the Ukrainian SSR it was 50% of all registered voters).

There is no mandatory vote, it's voluntary voting [8].

Characteristics of the form of state – a unitary state (with the annexed Autonomous Republic of Crimea and temporarily occupied parts of Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts).

Alternative voting methods – early voting, voting with absentee ballots, voting outside the polling station ('at home', at the place of residence).

Type of election – national presidential.

The level of competition was low, sluggish, and the election race was not characterized by a high level of tension. The society was confused, exhausted and vulnerable, and did not have the resources to participate in a fierce election race [7].

The list and characteristics of electoral actors – the first three candidates, which included Petro Poroshenko, a confectionery millionaire, business oligarch, nicknamed the 'chocolate king', who defended the values of the Maidan movement and supported it from the very beginning; Yulia Tymoshenko, a rival of V. Yanukovich (including in the 2010 elections) who headed the country's second largest party, Batkivshchyna, and was imprisoned on charges of abuse of office; Vitalii Klychko, an ambitious former boxer who was a prominent figure during the Euromaidan protests, headed the UDAR party and had a name untainted by corruption at the time [4].

Petro Poroshenko was a real candidate for the presidency and had many resources, personal and professional qualities. Yulia Tymoshenko was perceived by voters as a throwback to the past, a person associated

with corruption scandals and 'productive relations' with Russia and the Russian president personally during her premiership. Other outsiders/marginalized candidates were Olha Bohomolets, the 'white angel'; Dmytro Yarosh, leader of the far-right group 'Right Sector'; Mykhailo Dobkin, suspected of encroaching on the territorial integrity of Ukraine, and others.

Subsequently, V. Klychko announced that he would not run for president but would instead give his support to P. Poroshenko and consider running for the mayor of Kyiv [2].

The nature of the election campaign, the level of fraud, corruption and transparency – the 2014 campaign was characterized by sluggishness, unevenness and episodic nature. Due to objective circumstances, the security and political situation in the country, the re-election campaign was more active in the central and western regions of the country and was accompanied by provocations in the eastern and southern regions, sporadic personal visits and meetings with voters (mainly in the regions of influence); outdoor advertising was practically absent, political advertising was austere, indirect or even hidden – candidates tried to refrain from mass campaigning, the slightest manifestation of which was often accompanied by provocations. It is worth noting that almost every candidate tried to dissociate themselves from specific parties and political forces, and therefore identified themselves as 'self-nominated' (70% of the total). It was also almost the first time that current officials at the highest echelons of state power did not run for office, and as a result, the administrative resource was practically not used. Scientists, national and international observers have noted a low level of bribery, fraud, and cheating in the elections. The obvious winner from the very beginning of the election campaign, the first candidate's confident position practically leveled the intensity of the election race and the level of competition. Thus, Petro Poroshenko made every effort to distance himself from any scandals, intrigues, manipulations and speculations. For example, he refused to take part in TV debates. Yulia Tymoshenko, in turn, called for the abandonment of political advertising and the allocation of all resources to the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The security and military issues, issues of justice, integrity of the state, and prevention of repeating mistakes and scenarios were particularly acute. The figures reflecting the total expenses of candidates on the election campaign are demonstrative – three times less than in the similar elections of 2010. Ultra-nationalist candidates also did not receive sufficient voter support.

Simultaneity of the elections – in parallel with the presidential elections, early local elections were held, which were organized by the same precinct election commissions. Probably, simultaneous elections had a positive impact on the turnout, but it created inconveniences for voters (long queues, long waiting times, crowding, etc.).

Level of political culture and consciousness. Taking into account the voter turnout and the conditions of the 2014 election process, as well as the political context, we can assess the level of political culture as

'above average'. Although, the turnout was characterized by rather low rates (within the normal range), the level of mobilization, cohesion, political certainty, the level of fraud, and the percentage of spoiled ballots indicate a fairly developed electoral culture and the defense of civil rights [3].

The type of political ideology is liberalism, with still strong leftist sentiments in the east and rightist sentiments in the west and center. The annexation of the Crimean peninsula and the occupation of parts of Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts, in addition to creating confusion, provided an opportunity to make a decision and choose in favor of pan-European values and Euro-Atlantic aspirations.

The type of political regime is unstable (hybrid, transitional) democracy (just after the revolution). According to the Freedom House index as of 2014 (January 1, 2013 – December 31, 2013), Ukraine is a partially free democracy with a score of '4' (political rights) and '3' (civil liberties), where 7 is the best and 1 is the worst; as of 2015 (January 1, 2014 – December 31, 2014), Ukraine is a partially free democracy with a score of '3' (political rights) and '3' (civil liberties).

Trust in government – public authorities were discredited, and trust could be evaluated as extremely low.

Media coverage. The inactive election campaign was accompanied by low media activity. The most active candidate was O. Liashko, who constantly visited TV channels and shocked the electorate with his eccentric behavior.

So, why did Ukrainians not vote and why was the turnout so low even after the nation's confirmed 'blood' desire to move toward the ideals of democracy and its intransigent attitude toward the actions of the pro-Russian government?

Most experts agree and name the main reasons for this – the occupation of the territories, the loss of votes from at least two regions and the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, the departure of a significant number of citizens abroad, the impossibility of organizing the electoral process in Donbas, as well as bureaucratic obstacles and the human/political reluctance of some IDPs to change their voting place (personally visit the voter register department, fill out an application indicating the desired polling station or address, provide justification for the temporary change of address, and have originals and copies of identification documents with them). However, even if all the manipulations are carried out and the decision to change the polling station is positive, voters will not be able to vote for candidates in the constituencies and local elections.

However, if we look at, say, Kyiv or Odesa and Kharkiv oblasts, where the turnout rate was the same +_50%, this hypothesis is not confirmed.

In our opinion, an important factor behind the 2014 non-participation in the elections was the factor of electorate confusion, loss of guidelines and values, disorientation, rejection of the situation and lack of alternatives. Indeed, in early 2014, candidates from the opposition Party of Regions, the Communist Party of Ukraine and others did not conduct an active election campaign, and even if they did, they wouldn't receive electoral support and trust. According to the results of

the 2014 elections, S. Tihipko (Strong Ukraine) and M. Dobkin (self-nominated / ex-Party of Regions) took the 5th (5.23% of votes) and 6th (3.03%) places in the general list, respectively. As demonstrated, most of the representatives of the ex-governmental majority took a wait-and-see attitude, often being perceived as marginalized (which was atypical). Although, as can be seen from previous elections, preferences and the distribution of political forces, a significant number of citizens supported these political forces, their candidates and associates. The absence of such alternatives, along with disappointment in their predecessors, forced a significant number of Ukrainians to stay home and not vote. At the same time, the acute rejection of the Russian Federation and everything associated with 'Russian' and 'prison' helped the fifth president of Ukraine mobilize society and win the first round with 54.70% as opposed to his opponent's 12.81%. It should be noted that this is the second unprecedented victory in the first round of the presidential election in Ukraine [6].

References

1. Вибори Президента України 2014. Хід голосування по регіонах України. ЦЕНТРАЛЬНА ВИБОРЧА КОМІСІЯ: веб-сайт. URL: <https://www.cvk.gov.ua/pls/vp2014/wp001.html> (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
2. Жемчужникова К. Історія виборів: виборчі системи в Україні. ОПОРА: веб-сайт. URL: <https://www.oporaua.org/vybyry/istoriia-viboriv-viborchi-sistemi-v-ukrayini-22821> (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
3. Золотарьова Я. Історія виборів: у травні 2014 року українці обрали Президента в першому турі. ОПОРА: веб-сайт. URL: https://www.oporaua.org/vybyry/vybyry_prezydenta_2014-23088 (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
4. Парламентські вибори-2014: підсумки Національного екзит-полу'2014. Громадський простір: веб-сайт. URL: <https://www.prostir.ua/?news=parlamentski-vybyry-2014-pidsumky-natsionalnoho-ekzyt-polu2014> (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
5. Позачергові вибори Президента України 26 жовтня 2014 року: Інформаційно-аналітичне видання. / М.В. Охендовський, А.Й. Магера, Ж.І. Усенко-Чорна та ін. – К.: ВАІТЕ, 2016. – 456 с.
6. Процюк А., Горбаль А. Історична явка (2010-2019). Український центр суспільних даних: веб-сайт. URL: <https://socialdata.org.ua/istorichna-yavka-2010-2019/> (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
7. Червоненко В. Вибори-2014: старі політики під новими брендами. BBC Україна: веб-сайт. URL: https://www.bbc.com/ukrainian/politics/2014/09/140923_new_parties_vc (дата звернення: 2.14.2025)
8. Ю. Ключковський: 50-процентний поріг явки виборців є анахронізмом. РБК-Україна: веб-сайт. URL: https://www.rbc.ua/ukr/news/yu_klyuchkovskiy_50_protsentnyy_porog_yavki_izbirately_yavlyaetsy

a_anahronizmom__1181054600 (дата звернення:
2.14.2025)

веб-сайт. URL: <https://pl.suspilne.media/news/19451>
(дата звернення: 2.14.2025)

9. Як відбувалися вибори Президента
України з часів незалежності. Суспільне Полтава: